

EXPLORING EMOTIONAL COMPETENCE AMONG SCHOOL & HIGHER EDUCATION LEVEL STUDENTS: A REVIEW

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Abstract

In the contemporary world, students grapple with diverse social and emotional challenges, necessitating the acquisition of Emotional Competence for a harmonious and orderly life. This study delves into the current state of emotional competence among both school and higher education students, focusing on adolescents and adults. By examining numerous studies, this paper offers insights into the impact of emotional competence on higher education students, benefiting research experts and academics. The study tried to follow the systematic literature review method for the entire study.

Keywords: Emotional Competence, School Students, Adolescents, Higher Education Students.

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1. Introduction

In today's complex society, both students and adults contend with a range of challenges, from emotional and social issues to societal problems like communism, drug misuse, and inequality. Emotional competence is essential for achieving a balanced and organized life, particularly for higher education students, enabling them to navigate these challenges effectively. Emotional competence is gaining widespread attention as a strong predictor of life success (Qualter, 2007). Emotional competence (EC) can be viewed as a set of universal abilities applicable to various emotion-related tasks (Garner, 2010). Emotional competence includes recognizing emotions and variations in how people manage and address emotionally charged situations (Ciarrochi and Scott, 2006). This study aims to address a significant knowledge gap, particularly among higher education students, by investigating emotional competence research, especially in the context of India and abroad. It will examine prior studies to identify contemporary trends both domestically and internationally.

2. Significance of the Study

Literature reviews on emotional competence have played a vital role in highlighting its impact on society and education. These reviews have underscored the significance of empathy in this context (Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D. R. 2004), Effective communication, leadership, and conflict resolution are essential for building and sustaining healthy relationships (Goleman, 1995, 1998, 2002). Increased awareness of emotional competence has promoted stronger connections among individuals and groups, reducing misunderstandings, and positively influencing students' overall well-being and academic success. Emotional competence is vital for a supportive learning environment, aiding students in stress management and active engagement in the learning process (Brackett, et al. 2011). Research on emotional competency has enriched our understanding of how emotions impact both societal dynamics and individual behavior. These studies have facilitated the development of methods

and interventions that promote healthy relationships, effective communication, and overall well-being across various societal contexts, bridging the research-practice gap.

3. Conceptual Analysis of Emotional Competence

Author Name & Year	Definitions
Coleman, 1970	Emotional competence comprises five competencies: Adequate Depth of Feeling (ADF), Adequate Expression and Control of Emotions (AECE), Ability to Function with Emotions (AFE), Ability to Cope with Problem Emotions (ACPE), and Ability to Enhance Positive Emotions (AEPE). These competencies collectively enable effective management of interconnected emotional processes.
Salovey & Mayer, 1990	Emotional competence involves recognizing, differentiating, and using emotions, both one's own and others', to guide decisions and actions.
Goleman, 1995, 1998	Emotional competence is the capacity to harness and utilize emotions for motivation, understanding, confidence, creativity, and the influence of others.
Kierstead, 1999	Emotional competence is gauged by personal skills (self-management) and social skills (interactions with others).
Saarni, 1999	Emotional competence involves recognizing inner emotions, their external expression, understanding emotions' role in relationships, and nurturing one's human potential.
Wong and Law, 2002	Emotional competence development should emphasize practicality, linking improved emotional regulation to greater self-assurance, effective environmental management, and the promotion of entrepreneurial behavior.
Ciarrochi, Deane & Anderson, 2002	Individual variations in people's ability to effectively manage their emotions and emotional issues.
Brackett and Mayer, 2003	Emotional competence involves using advanced processes related to attitudes towards emotions, emotional clarity, distinguishing between emotions, and mood regulation.
Flowers, 2005	Emotional competence entails effectively managing one's own and others' emotions, as well as handling external relationships and situations.
Wakeman, 2006	Accurate self-identification of emotions can foster emotional competence in areas like conflict resolution and empathy.
Santrock, 2008	Understanding, using, and appropriately managing (expressing) emotions is known as emotional competence (EC).
Salovey, 1990, Cherniss, 2000; Giardini & Frese, 2008	Emotional competence encompasses the skill set of perceiving, understanding, and effectively managing emotional information for oneself and others.

Seal & Andrews-Brown, 2010	Emotional competence includes social awareness, proficient social skills, and emotional self-control.
Harrison & Fopma-Loy, 2010	Emotional Competence involves using emotions to improve thinking by applying emotional reasoning and control.

4. Research Question

- i. What are the Current research trends on Emotional Competence in India & abroad with respect to School level & Higher education level students?

5. Method

The researcher conducted a systematic literature review to explore emotional competence in school and higher education students. They examined studies from the earliest to the most recent to understand current trends in this area in India and globally.

a. Literature Search Strategy

The researcher analysed papers and theses published from 2015 to 2022 using various keywords like competence, social emotional competences, young adults, adolescents, university students, college students, and primary school children to define emotional competence development.

b. Selection Criteria

The study focused on adolescents, including students in grades 5-12 and first-year undergraduates. It also included college and university students aged 18-24. The researcher selected papers and theses from 2015 to 2022 meeting these criteria.

6. Objectives of the Study

1. To review pertinent research on Emotional Competence among college & university-going students that is currently available.
2. To review relevant, recently published studies on adolescents & pre-primary level children who are attending schools with regard to Emotional Competence.

Table 1.1: School-Related Emotional Competence Research Synthesis

Author	Year	Country	Purpose of the study	Research Method, Design, Sample size	Major Finding & Conclusion
Butvilas, T. & Kovaite, K.	2022	Lithuania	Lithuanian students in grades 5-12 explored socio-emotional competence as a creativity catalyst in younger teens.	a) Quantitative b) Comparative Study c) 1322	This study demonstrated gender variations in socio-emotional skills: Females prioritized personal values, admiration, emotional perception, balance, and support, while males focused on self-esteem, stress management, positivism,

					authenticity, and humor.
Kumari, N.	2021	India	This study sought to examine the relationships among academic achievement, locality, gender, and emotional maturity.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 562	The results of the study showed that gender and emotional competence had a substantial impact on students' academic achievement, whereas locality had no main influence.
Channigavi, A.-S.	2021	India	The study wanted to examine the effects of parental education, emotional maturity, and academic stress on adolescents' school adjustment while taking sociodemographic characteristics like gender, location, and institution type into consideration.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 500	The study found that lower parental education had a negative impact on students' school adjustment, emphasizing the role of parental expectations in academic stress. Strong emotional competence positively influenced school adjustment, especially in terms of location. Notably, emotional competency had a greater positive effect on boys' school adjustment compared to girls.
Raundeley, S.	2020	India	There were two sections to the investigation. First, it looked at	a) Quantitative	This study discovered that suicide ideation had a

			how emotional competence, self-oriented perfectionism, and stressful life events affect adolescent suicidal thoughts. The second section investigated the connections between teenage emotional competence, self-oriented perfectionism, and stressful life events.	b) Correlational Design c) 107	negative link with emotional competence but was positively correlated with stressful life events and self-oriented perfectionism. While stressful life experiences and self-centered perfectionism exhibited lesser relationships with adolescent suicidal ideation, emotional competence was a reliable predictor of suicidal ideation.
Sonia	2019	India	The study sought to analyze emotional competence mean scores in experimental and control groups, considering gender, and assess the impact of gender on students' emotional competence following experimental treatment.	a) Quantitative b) Experimental Research Design c) 64	Prior to treatment, the study observed no appreciable variation in the mean emotional competence scores between the experimental and control groups. Boys demonstrated higher levels of emotional competence than girls after the experimental treatment, though gender had a significant impact.
Gomathi, E.	2018	India	The researcher studied stress management, emotional competence, lifestyle, and self-concept among	a) Qualitative b) Normative Survey Method c) 1025	Result revealed that strong link existed between stress management, lifestyle, and emotional

			standard XI students while considering gender and socio-demographic factors. The goal was to explore how these factors, particularly self-concept, lifestyle, and emotional competency, influenced the students' ability to manage stress.		competency. Additionally, it discovered a substantial gender-based link between self-concept and stress management. Students from joint families had higher levels of emotional competence, self-concept, stress management, and a healthier lifestyle when it came to family type.
Sangeeta	2018	India	The study's objective was to investigate the relationships among emotional competence, learning styles, and decision-making preferences in senior secondary students with regard to demographic variables like gender, locality, type of school, and academic stream.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 400	The study found a substantial negative link between emotional competence, learning preferences, and decision-making preferences. In addition, research discovered that there were no appreciable differences in emotional competence between males and girls in senior secondary pupils based on location, school type, or academic stream.
Baruah, K.	2018	India	The researcher examined gender differences in parent-adolescent	a) Quantitative	The study revealed notable gender differences in

			relationships and social-emotional competences among adolescents. The study explored how these variables interacted and influenced adolescent social and emotional competence.	b) Descriptive Method c) 300	adolescents' social and emotional competencies and parent-adolescent relationships. While parent-adolescent connections had a significant impact on emotional competence for both genders, there was no significant correlation with social competence. Interestingly, adolescent boys exhibited higher emotional competence compared to girls.
Arora, S. & Kaur, S.	2017	India	The study aimed to assess gender-based differences in emotional competence and investigate the relationship between emotional competence and depression.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Method c) 600	The study found no significant gender-based difference in emotional competence and identified a negative relationship between emotional competence and depression.
Dahiya, S., & Kanta	2017	India	The researcher aimed to investigate the relationships between academic achievement and emotional competence, learning style, as	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 300	The study's findings indicated positive relationships between academic achievement and emotional competence,

			well as academic anxiety.		learning style, as well as academic anxiety among 9th-grade students.
Kataria, S.	2016	India	Researcher wanted to investigate the level of aggression among 10th standard adolescents with Emotional Competence.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 100	The study found no significant difference between boys and girls in terms of emotional competence and aggression among adolescent students.
Bhutani, S.	2016	India	The researcher aimed to explore the connection between parental involvement, emotional competency, and academic stress among senior secondary school students.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 300	The study's findings indicated a positive and significant relationship between parental involvement and academic stress, while there was a negative and significant relationship between emotional competence and academic stress.
Lopez-Gonzalez, L. & Oriol, X.	2016	Spain	This study sought to determine the relationship between academic achievement, classroom climate, and emotional competence in 420 secondary school students.	a) Quantitative b) Mediation Analysis c) 420	Results revealed inequalities in educational attainment by gender. Only educational attainment was associated to differences in classroom atmosphere. Through the use of mediation analysis, it was discovered that classroom

					dynamics and academic success were both highly impacted by the environment of the classroom.
Kumar, A.	2015	India	The researcher aimed to investigate the relationship between self-concept and emotional competence among secondary school students, considering gender differences.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 200	The study found no significant relationship between self-concept and emotional competence among students. However, a significant gender difference was observed in emotional competence, with girls being more emotionally competent than boys among secondary school students.
Sajeev, B. & Bani, M.	2015	India	The study aimed to explore the relationship between meta-cognition and emotional competence among 11th-grade students in Chhattisgarh, as well as to assess gender-based differences in these factors and their impact on academic achievement.	a) Quantitative b) Correlational Method c) 600	The study found a positive relationship between emotional competence and academic achievement among 11th-grade students in Chhattisgarh. Gender did not impact this relationship. Notably, rural students displayed higher emotional competence levels compared

					to their urban counterparts.
Kumar, A., and Thapar, V.	2015	India	The study examined the connection between adjustment and emotional competence among secondary school students in Ludhiana district, focusing on urban males and rural girls from nuclear households.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 200	The study found a significant link between emotional competence and adjustment, along with notable differences in emotional competence among secondary school students from nuclear families in both rural and urban areas, as well as between genders.
Masrat, R., Wani, M.A., and Alam	2015	India	This study examined adolescents from Aligarh Muslim University in Uttar Pradesh to explore the relationship between emotional competence and general well-being.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 100	The study found that emotional competence in male adolescents strongly predicted mental, social, emotional, and spiritual well-being but had no significant impact on physical well-being. Conversely, emotional competence in female adolescents significantly predicted both physical and emotional well-being but did not significantly affect mental, social, and spiritual well-being.

Table 1.2: Higher Education-Related Emotional Competence Research Synthesis

Author	Year	Country	Purpose of the study	Research Method, Design, Sample Size	Major Finding & Conclusion
Wang, Y., et al.	2022	China	This study focused on online learning readiness and emotional competence as essential characteristics to explore their implications for students' academic success during the COVID-19 period.	a) Quantitative b) Survey Method c) 1316 & 668	The study found a significant link between high school students' readiness for online learning, emotional competence, and academic success during COVID-19. For college students, online learning preparedness was the key factor for academic success. Both online learning readiness and emotional competence contributed to adolescent resilience and online learning success during the pandemic.
Punia, P., Khokhar, S. & Phor, M.	2022	India	The goal of this study was to examine the connections between college students' emotional competence, emotional intelligence, and anxiety.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 100	College students generally reported high anxiety levels and moderate emotional competence. Location (rural vs. urban) did not impact anxiety or emotional competence. A weakly positive relationship was found between anxiety and emotional intelligence.

Huezo-Ponce, L. & Fernández-Pérez, V. & Rodríguez-Ariza, L.	2021	Mexico	This study aimed to assess the influence of emotional competence on entrepreneurial training in a private university setting, using a modified version of Ajzen's theory of planned behaviour.	a) Quantitative b) Experimental Study c) 217, 1690	The outcomes were contrasted with those from a different university ecosystem in the same region. This study provided useful recommendations for enhancing entrepreneurship programmes that support the development of college students' entrepreneurial and self-employment skills.
Margreat, J.	2021	India	This study sought to determine whether Cognitive Behaviour Therapy helped improve college students' emotional maturity, self-esteem, and opinions of their bodies.	a) Quantitative b) Follow-up c) 48	This study found that Cognitive Behaviour Therapy was beneficial in lowering negative body image beliefs, enhancing emotional competence, and raising self-esteem in college students, hence promoting beneficial modifications.
Chien-Chi, et.al. (2020)	2020	China	This study wanted to examine the connection between emotional skills, entrepreneurial self-	a) Quantitative b) Questionnaire Survey c) 312	Study outcomes; i) Entrepreneurial intention linked positively with social-emotional competence. ii) There were significant connections between self-efficacy in all domains and the intention to start a business. iii) Emotional intelligence

			efficacy, and entrepreneurial intention among college students.		greatly increased entrepreneurial self-efficacy. iv) Self-efficacy served as a mediator between emotional competence and entrepreneurial intention. Increased entrepreneurial self-efficacy results from developing emotional abilities.
Chishi, I.-V.	2018	India	The study investigated how gender, locality, and academic stream influenced academic achievement and emotional competence in college students. It also explored the connection between academic adjustment and emotional competence.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 1000	The results of this study indicated that there were notable differences in academic achievement and emotional competence among college students based on gender, location, and stream. Additionally, researchers discovered a bad association between college students' academic adjustment and emotional competence.
Jomon, K.J. & Romate, J.	2017	India	In Kerala, first-year undergraduate students were studied for gender disparities in emotional competence.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 600	In first-year college students, the study found a strong correlation between emotional competence and participation in class. Furthermore, emotional competence varied significantly by gender and college type, with male students and those attending government colleges scoring better than

			e, and researchers looked into the relationships between emotional competence and student engagement.		female students and those attending aided and private institutions.
William, V.J.	2017	India	The researcher sought to evaluate the emotional competence of college students in Tamil Nadu in relation to their gender, place of residence, and field of study.	a) Quantitative b) Descriptive Survey c) 408	The study found gender and academic field differences in emotional competence. Science students outperformed art students, and females outscored males. No significant differences were observed between rural and urban areas.
Tarabakina, L. V. et al.	2015	Russia	The study investigated 100 senior students from Moscow and Nizhny Novgorod universities, exploring the connection between emotional creativity indicators and	a) Quantitative b) Experimental Study c) 100	The study revealed positive links between emotional creativity and communication competence while noting negative associations with dominance, conservatism, and conformity. The results emphasized the need to nurture students' emotional and creative identities through interactive, reflective learning approaches that enhance emotional appeal.

			communication styles.		
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7. Limitation of the study

- i. The study concentrated only on students in educational settings, omitting professors and administrators.
- ii. It focussed only on the Emotional Competence among the students and different research synthesis on Emotional Competence
- iii. It focussed only on studies related to Emotional Competence from 2015 till 2022.

8. Implication for further research

This study focused on Emotional Competence among students in school and higher education. Future research may be done on areas like on B.Ed. trainees, teachers at all levels, public and private sector employees, and among the children who are related with juvenile issues. Further exploration can consider emotional competence in teacher-student, parent-child dynamics, and across various professions.

9. Conclusion

This study, which drew from a variety of disciplines and previous research, examined emotional competence the capacity to communicate emotions effectively among adolescent and adult students. Enhancing emotional competence fosters self-confidence, positive relationships, stress resilience, and effective resource management in personal and professional life (Chien-Chi, et al. 2020). Besides, enhancing emotional competence benefits personal and social functioning (Kotsou, I. et al. 2011). This article's findings will aid researchers and educators in understanding the impact of emotional competence on students and professionals across higher education sectors.

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